

INFLUENCE OF THE AGE HARDENING OF Al ALLOY MATRIX ON THE MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF C/Al COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

TEM characterisation of interphases and precipitates formed during the processing or heat-treatments clarifies the influence of alloying elements on the mechanical behaviour of C/Al composites. In FT700/Al-4.5Cu composites, Al₂Cu primary phase which edges the fibres results in good composite strength because the weakly bonded Al₂Cu/fibre interface acts as mechanical fuse. On the contrary, in M40J/A357, the Si/fibre interface is not weak enough and Si precipitates promote formation and propagation of cracks and result in low composite strength. Their detrimental effect is limited by a fibre coating of pyrolytic carbon.

INTRODUCTION

Aluminium matrix composites reinforced with carbon fibres are investigated as aerospace and automotive materials. A large amount of work has already been performed to optimize the process [1-4]. Composites can henceforth be considered as structural elements or local reinforcement of components. In the last application, industrial aluminium alloys are of interest to optimize the mechanical behaviour of the unreinforced parts of the components. The use of such alloys as matrix in composites can result in deleterious brittle interphases due both to fibre-matrix reaction and to precipitation of intermetallic phases during the process or subsequent heat-treatments. The design of composites of high mechanical properties implies to detect and identify the possible reaction products and intermetallic precipitates, to rely these microstructural characteristics with the mechanical behaviour and finally to optimize the processing conditions. Such an approach is developed in MMC processed with two alloys containing a high level of alloying elements, A357(AS7G0.6) and Al-4.5Cu reinforced with carbon fibres of high strength or high modulus, M40J and FT700 respectively.

In 1D-FT700 fibres/Al-4.5 Cu matrix composite processed at 918°K, large Al₂Cu primary grains (\approx 1micrometer) are revealed at the fibre/matrix interfaces by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) [5]. Al₂Cu was dissolved in a solution treatment at 803°K whose duration was selected in order to minimize the formation of brittle Al₄C₃. After 6 hours at 803°K, no interphase is detected by SEM. The composites were then aged at room temperature (composite A) or 18 hours at 433°K (composite B). Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) investigation of the composites was performed to determine the efficiency of the heat-treatments to minimize Al₄C₃ formation and to promote redissolution of primary phases and age-hardening of the matrix. The origin of the mechanical behaviour of the composites is derived from this study.

In 1D-M40J/A357 composite processed at 893°K (material C), SEM observations reveal many Si precipitates and a few Mg₂Si precipitates (several hundreds nm in size). Although irregularly spread in the matrix, these brittle phases are detrimental to the composite strength (\approx 700 MPa). Heat-treatments do not improve the strength. They indeed result in a dissolution of Mg₂Si but

not of Si which has a low solubility in solid aluminium. Moreover, they promote Al_4C_3 formation and, if the duration of heat-treatment is too long, the composite strength drops.

One method to enhance composite strength is to create an interface of weak failure resistance which deviates cracks and thus acts as a mechanical fuse. Such a goal may be achieved using a thin fibre coating of pyrolytic carbon (Cp) [4]. Cp coating (a few tens nm) was successfully used in T800 fibres-Al matrix composites [6,7]. In the present work, a Cp coating significantly improved the strength of 1D-M40J/Cp/A357 as-cast composite (material D) which reaches about 1300 MPa.

According to SEM observations, the repartition and size of the primary phases are similar in the C and D composites. Moreover, no Al_4C_3 is revealed. All the microstructural difference should consist in the Cp coating. TEM investigations were necessary firstly to verify the repartition of the primary phases, secondly to reveal the fibre coating and characterize its thickness and structure and finally to identify the possible reaction products. Their results are used to discuss the efficiency of the processing and the mechanical properties of the composites.

MATERIALS

1D-composites plates (1 mm thick) were fabricated at ONERA by liquid infiltration of carbon fibre preforms under moderate pressure and isothermal conditions [9,10]. Under such conditions and using alloys with low liquidus temperature such as Al-4.5Cu and A357 (Si=6.7, Mg=0.65, Fe= 0.1w%), fibre-matrix reaction is significantly reduced if not avoided.

The alloys were elaborated either at ONERA (Al-4.5Cu) or by Messier supplier (A357). FT700 fibres ($\sigma_r = 3800$ Mpa, $E = 700$ GPa) is provided by Toray and M40J fibres ($\sigma_r = 4400$ Mpa, $E=370$ GPa) by Tonen. Some M40J yarns were coated with pyrolytic carbon applied by low pressure chemical vapor deposition [8].

FT700/Al-4.5Cu were pressed during 60s at 918°K. The volume fraction of fibres was about 55%. As-cast composites were heat-treated 6 hours at 803°K and water quenched to room temperature. Composite A was then aged at room temperature and composite B 6 hours at 433°K. Such heat-treatments correspond to the T4 and T6 heat-treatments of the alloy respectively. The as-cast M40J/A357 (C) and M40J/Cp/A357 (D) composites were pressed during 60s at 893°K. They contained about 70% of fibres.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Thin foils whose plane was perpendicular or parallel to the fibre axis were prepared. They were thinned down to forty micrometers by mechanical grinding and then ion milled.

Ion milling corresponds to an anneal of about 8 hours at a temperature which reaches 423-473K in the thinnest parts. This means that the composites are submitted to an additional T6 heat-treatment. Such an anneal has no effect on the as-cast C and D composites. It cannot change the residual primary phase or enhance the reaction scale in the A and B composites. Such a heat-treatment promotes the formation of θ'' precipitates and possibly the beginning of θ' precipitation in the Al-4.5Cu alloy [9]. It likely modifies the amount of these precipitates in the composites. However, it will be shown later that the location but not the amount of precipitates provides informations which clarify the formation of the primary phase. In this paper, we only discuss the origin and the repartition of the primary phase and reaction product in the composites, phases which play the major role on the mechanical behaviour as it will be shown later on.

Electronic diffraction, bright field and high resolution images, EDX analyses were performed at 300 keV in a Philips CM30 (Scherzer resolution 2.3 mm). EDX analyses were realised with a 12 nm probe size using Ultra Thin Window Si-Li detector (Link); the sample had to be tilted of 20°.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

FT700 FIBRES/Al-4.5Cu MATRIX COMPOSITES

The microstructure of both A and B composites exhibits two distinct features, one of them being the most commonly observed in the two materials.

Microstructure the most commonly observed in FT700/Al-4.5Cu composites:

- Interfaces in the A and B composites:

The fibres are edged with grains of dark contrast in bright field images (white arrows fig.1&2). The layer is rather continuous but does not wrap completely the fibres (fig.2). Its width ranges from 10 to 30 nm. The grains are composed of Al and Cu. EDX quantitative analysis of the thinnest grains show they consist of Al_2Cu (fig.3). The grains exhibit no particular orientation relationship with the surrounding phases, fibre or matrix.

Al_4C_3 grains were never revealed either by their typical rectangular shape on bright field images (cf. discussion) or by EDX analysis.

Numerous cracks propagate through the foils, even in thickest zones (fig.4). They always develop between the Al_2Cu layer and the fibre (black arrows fig. 1&2).

- Matrix in the A and B composite:

The matrix contains lamellar precipitates, with dark contrast in bright field images, which lie in perpendicular directions (fig.1). These precipitates, are 5-10 nm thick and 50-100 or 150-250 nm long. EDX analyses show they contain Al and Cu. Because of their size, the influence of the surrounding matrix is not excluded on quantitative analysis. They were thus characterized by electronic diffraction (fig.2, 5). The patterns show that the precipitates are coherent with the matrix, some of them at least exhibiting a substructure. They lie in the {100} Al planes.

The lamellar precipitates are always regularly spread in the matrix. Lamellar Precipitate Free zones (PFZ) were never observed next to the interface that is to say next to the Al_2Cu layer.

- Matrix grain boundaries in A and B composites:

The general grain boundaries, that is to say the boundaries between grains which exhibit no particular orientation relationships, contain grains of dark contrast in the A and B composites (fig.6). These grains are composed of Al_2Cu . They are much larger than the lamellar precipitates and are incoherent with the neighbouring matrix grains. There is no PFZ (zone without lamellar precipitate) next to these boundaries.

Microstructure observed in some zones of FT700/Al-4.5Cu composites:

- Interfaces:

The features of the interfaces are similar as above except the size of the Al_2Cu grains which reaches several hundreds nm (fig.7). Al_4C_3 grains were exceptions at these interfaces.

- Matrix:

The matrix contains large Al_2Cu grains (\approx a few hundreds nm) incoherent with the matrix. Lamellar precipitates are extremely rare in these zones.

Discussion of the mechanical behaviour of the FT700/Al-4.5Cu composites

An Al_2Cu layer is revealed by MET both in A and B composites. What is the origin of this layer? During age-hardening of the alloy, thermodynamic equilibria are reached by precipitation of Guinier-Preston (GP) zones (T4) or lamellar precipitates (θ'' or θ') coherent with the matrix (T6). It is known that preferential precipitation of intermetallic phases occurs in the grainboundaries of the alloy resulting in the formation of Precipitate Free Zones (PFZ) [9] on both side of the grainboundaries. Preferential precipitation was also observed at the interfaces in as-cast materials. In the composites, no PFZ are detectable along the interfaces or general grain-boundaries which are nevertheless decorated by Al_2Cu grains. This means that preferential precipitation does not starts at the grain-boundary and thus does not decrease the Cu content next to the boundary preventing the precipitate nucleation. Thus, Al_2Cu grains are residual grains of the primary precipitation.

The repartition of Al_2Cu grains in the composites confirms the model of solidification proposed by Gungor et al. [10]: Nucleation of dendrites on the fibres and growth of secondary arms of dendrites in a parallel direction with the fibre axis. The concentration of copper increases in the

residual liquid which is rejected at the periphery of the arms. This implies a preferential precipitation of Al_2Cu along fibres as experimentally observed and may explain the enrichment in Al_2Cu of some interfaces and of the neighbouring matrix.

Al_4C_3 was not detected between fibre and matrix. EDX analysis may miss Al_4C_3 because in tilted samples, number of grains are not suitable for EDX analysis. Previous studies of T800/Al and T800/Cp/Al composites showed that Al_4C_3 always grows in the shape of needle elongated in a direction parallel to the $\langle 0001 \rangle$ axis and that such a morphology is clearly revealed on bright field images provided that the grain size exceeds a few nm [6]. Examples of this needle shape is shown in M40J/A357 (fig.10,14). At the FT700/Al interfaces, such needles were never observed. Some Al_4C_3 seeds (a few nm) may be located in between the Al_2Cu grains but they can hardly be detected. As a matter of fact, they were not enough numerous to increase the fibre-matrix bonding so that the composite strength drops. If some reaction products can exit, we can nevertheless conclude that, typically, there is no reaction layer at the interfaces.

Both the low reactivity of the fibres and the infiltration conditions (temperature and duration) limit the reaction and thus the formation (if any) of Al_4C_3 . As long as the Al_2Cu layer is not dissolved by the dissolution treatment, the reaction between Al and C implies a diffusion through the Al_2Cu layer and the formation of Al_4C_3 is very limited as experimentally observed. When a solution treatment of 24 hours at 803°K is performed, Al_2Cu is completely dissolved and large ($\approx 1\mu\text{m}$) Al_4C_3 grains can be formed as shown by MEB [5].

In thin foils, the stresses pre-existing in the composites or due to the sample grinding induce crack formation. These cracks always propagate between the Al_2Cu border and the fibre. It is known that preferential sputtering occurs at the interfaces which consequently become weaker than in the initial composite. However, this phenomena is counterbalanced by the different sputtering rate of the phases located at the interfaces. In the A and B composites, the Al_2Cu border is always thinned less rapidly than the neighbouring fibre and matrix and the matrix is always thinned the most rapidly. The preferential decohesion between the fibre and the Al_2Cu border thus results from a weaker adhesion of Al_2Cu with the fibre than with the matrix. The morphology of Al_2Cu grains sustain this conclusion. They are indeed imbedded in the matrix whereas the Al_2Cu /fibre interface is rather smooth. This weak bonding, protects the fibre against the cracks which develop in the neighbouring Al_2Cu border under stresses and thus smoothes down the deleterious effect of a brittle interphase.

As-cast and A (T4) composites exhibit similar strength ($\approx 1300\text{ MPa}$ [6]). Thus, T4 age-hardening does not determine the mechanical behaviour of the composite although it increases the strength and yield stress of the matrix. The mechanical properties of the composites are determined by the fibre/matrix interface strength which itself derives from the Al_2Cu border.

Figure 1: Composite B (FT700/Al4.5Cu). Image obtained with an Al zone axis $\approx \langle 100 \rangle$. White arrows show Al_2Cu grains.

Figure 2: Composite B (FT700/Al4.5Cu). Image obtained with an $\langle 110 \rangle$ Al zone axis.

Figure 3: EDX analysis of a grain of the fibre/matrix interfacial layer.

Figure 4: Cross-section of the B composite showing cracks along the interfaces.

Figure 5: Precipitates in the B composite: Bright field image and electronic diffraction obtained with a $\langle 100 \rangle_{Al}$ zone axis.

Figure 6: Grain boundary in B composite decorated with Al_2Cu grains

Figure 7: Zone in composite B where the interface and the matrix contain large Al_2Cu grains.

M40J FIBRE/A357 MATRIX AND M40J/Cp/A357 MATRIX COMPOSITES

The microstructure of the C and D composites exhibits significant similarities and differences.

Similarities of the microstructure of C and D composites.

The fibres are evenly distributed in the matrix (fig.8). However, because of their high volume fraction, number of them are in contact and the other are as near as a few tens nm (fig.10-13).

Si precipitates are numerous and regularly spread in the composites. They were identified by EDX analysis (fig.9). Large Si grains are regularly detected between fibres or at the points of contact of two fibres (fig.12,13). However, Si is not always observed in between fibres (fig.10,11). Si precipitates are rarely detected inside the matrix grains and besides they are as small as a few nm.

Mg₂Si precipitates, a few hundreds nm large, are exceptionally observed. They are located along the fibres. Small inclusions (a few tens nm) containing Mg were also detected in the matrix grains. They are irregularly spread in the composites.

In both composites, cracks develop during the foils preparation neither at the fibre/Al interfaces nor at the fibre/Si interfaces .

Differences between the microstructures of C and D composites.

In the D composite, MET investigations show that all the fibres are continuously surrounded by a Cp layer 15 to 30 nm thick (fig.11,13). Cp exhibits a turbostratic structure (fig.15). The basal planes are parallel to the surface. Images clearly show that the microstructure is much more lamellar in the Cp coating than in the fibre near surface (fig.14).

The amount of reaction product, Al₄C₃, differs significantly in the two composites. Al₄C₃ grows at the fibre/Al interface (fig.14) but was not observed in between fibres and Si precipitates. It forms needles of rectangular shape, typically 100x10 nm in size. These needles are discontinuously but regularly located at the fibre/Al interface in the C composite whereas they are very rare at the Cp/Al interface in the D composite (arrows in fig.10,11).

Discussion of the mechanical properties of M40J/A357 and M40J/Cp/A357

As-cast composites contain large amount of brittle phases, primary precipitates and reaction products. The repartition and size of Si, which is the main primary precipitate, is much the same in the C (M40J/A357) and D (M40J/Cp/A357) composites whereas the amount of Al₄C₃ differs.

Al₄C₃ needles, although of small size, edge regularly the fibre/Al interface whereas they are rare along the Cp/Al interface. The resistance to failure of the reinforcement/Al interface is thus higher in C than in D composites. It was shown that the strength of the reinforcement, M40J or coated M40J, is the same in the two composites [7]. Thus, the higher resistance to failure of the interface will result in the lowest composite strength. However, in M40J/Al-4.5Mg composite elaborated in the same conditions no strength loss due to Al₄C₃ is observed [11]. We think that Si but not Al₄C₃ is the major cause of the poor mechanical properties of the C composite.

The strikingness of the composite microstructure is indeed the large amount of Si fibre bridges which are regularly spread in the composites. These brittle bridges have obviously a deleterious influence on the mechanical behaviour. They increase the internal stresses next to fibres, they cause crack nucleation next to the fibres during the deformation and they promote fibre crack propagation from fibre to fibre and finally the rupture of the composite. The large difference between the strength of the two composites shows that the Cp interface prevents or at least smooths down these deleterious effects of the Si bridges. There is no experimental evidence which shows if the crack deflection occurs in the Cp or at the fibre/Cp or Cp/Si interface. But, whatever the crack propagation, it is clear that the resistance to failure is lower when a Cp interphase lies between Si and the fibre. The different resistance to failure of the let us called Cp/Si and fibre/Si interfaces can be related to the different microstructure of the fibre near surface (very distorted) and of the Cp (very lamellar).

As a conclusion, A357 alloy can be used if a weak interface between matrix and reinforcement can be obtained. These results confirm the determinant and beneficent influence of the Cp coating on the mechanical behaviour of aluminium matrix composites reinforced with carbon fibres.

Figure 8: Cross-section of the D composite (M40J/Cp/A357)

Figure 9: Typical EDX spectrum of large precipitates lying between fibres in C and D composites

Figure 14: M40J near surface and Al_4C_3 grain in Composite C.

Figure 15: Cp coating and M40J near surface in composite D.

Figure 10: Composite C (M40J/Al)

Figure 11: Composite D (M40J/Cp/Al)

Figure 12: Si precipitate in C composite.

Figure 13: Si precipitate in D composite.

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